

M²EED

**MMI and knowledge
Exchange Events
Design tool**

HOMEPAGE

Are you organising an event?

The M²EED online tool will support the design of Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML), and other events, enabling you to select the most appropriate type of event (i.e., conference, Focus group, etc.).

Once selected the event format, M²EED will support you to design the event planning the different activities and configuring the agenda, based on a series of event information parameters provided by the user.

At the bottom of the page, users can find the steps to follow in details

- 1) Select a suitable MML and knowledge exchange events format
- 2) Select the right activities
- 3) Customize the agenda
- 4) Download supporting documents

And a START button to make the process start.

CHALLENGE CLUSTER OF INTEREST

Which challenge cluster are you interested in?

A - Market development

B - Awareness and trust building

C - Supporting strategies and standards

D - Supporting environment

E - Regional/local development

I don't know

MEED requires that the users provides answers to a set of three questions; based on them the system will suggest the best event format.

Select the challenge cluster on which the event will focus on:

A – Market development

B – Awareness and trust building

C – Supporting strategies and standards

D – Supporting environment

E – Regional/local development

If there are any doubts about which one to choose, it is possible to select the “I don’t know” option.

At the right side of the page, there is the list of steps users should follow in order to complete the process. The current step is highlighted through a green background.

Tool steps

1. Select a suitable event format

2. Select the right activities

3. Customize the agenda

4. Download supporting documents

GROUP COMPOSITION

Users can indicate the target audience of the event selecting the group composition. Users can choose more than one option in order to create an homogeneous or an heterogeneous group. The “I don’t know” choice is also present.

In addition to the tool steps list described before, at the left side of the page there is the list of choices made by the user during the previous steps.

Choices you made

BIOVOICES Challenge Cluster
A - Market development

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for selecting group composition. At the top, there is a header with four icons representing different groups (Civil society, Public administration, Business, Research and education) and a question mark. Below the header, the text reads: "Which is the composition of the group you want to engage?" and "Please pick one or more choices". There are four rows of options, each with an icon and a checkbox:

- Civil society
- Public administration
- Business
- Research and education

At the bottom, there is an option "I don't know" with a checkbox . Below the list, there are two buttons: "BACK" and "NEXT".

BACK

NEXT

GROUP SIZE

Users can select the group size they want to engage. As per previous questions, users can choose the “I don’t know” option in case of doubt.

The screenshot shows a mobile app interface with a header image of a laptop displaying group icons and a question mark. Below the header is a question: "Which is the size of the group you want to engage?". There are four radio button options: "10-40" (selected), "< 10", "> 40", and "I don't know". A "BACK" button is located at the bottom of the screen.

Which is the size of the group you want to engage?

10-40

< 10

> 40

I don't know

BACK

The summary block is divided into two columns. The left column, titled "Choices you made", shows the selected "BIOVOICES Challenge Cluster" as "A - Market development" and "Group composition" as "Civil society" and "Public administration". The right column, titled "Tool steps", lists four steps: "1. Select a suitable event format", "2. Select the right activities", "3. Customize the agenda", and "4. Download supporting documents".

Choices you made

BIOVOICES Challenge Cluster
A - Market development

Group composition:
Civil society
Public administration

Tool steps

1. Select a suitable event format
2. Select the right activities
3. Customize the agenda
4. Download supporting documents

For each step made, the tool updates the right and left side lists.

SUGGESTED FORMATS

BACK

BACK

Users can access to the tool suggested formats list. Initially, the tool suggests 3 best choices, highlighted with a thumb-up icon, but users can click on the VIEW ALL SUGGESTIONS button to view all the available formats and their scores. Clicking on FACTSHEET button, users can view the specific format factsheets to gain more information about it.

CHOOSE A FORMAT

We suggest the following formats based on your parameters

<input checked="" type="radio"/> Virtual conferences	3.0	FACTSHEET
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Working group	3.0	FACTSHEET
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Unconference	3.0	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Knowledge fair and exhibitions	2.67	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Charrette Workshops	2.67	FACTSHEET
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Conference	2.67	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Virtual fair and exhibitions	2.67	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Future workshops	2.33	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Peer reviews	2.33	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Study visits	2.0	FACTSHEET
<input type="radio"/> Focus group	2.0	FACTSHEET

HIDE ALL SUGGESTIONS BUTTON

BACK

Users now can set a format clicking on the name of the chosen one.

You are choosing Unconference. Are you sure?

YES NO

After confirming your choice, we are going to select the suitable activities for the event

Clicking on Unconference format, for example, the tool asks users to confirm the choice.

AGENDA PREVIEW

After format confirmation, the tool shows the agenda structure.

For each format, the tool suggests a specific agenda, with different activities and sessions.

Agenda preview

This is the basic structure of the agenda regarding the format you chose. In the following steps, you'll be able to choose different activities for each section. Click on next to start!

Agenda Item	Description	Timeline	Suitable activities
		Phase 1: Setting the scene	
Kick-off	Participants arrive to the space, the facilitator(s) explains the rules of interaction, and the unconference agenda is collaboratively built.		
		Phase 2: Working phase	
Conversations/discussion groups	Mostly based on free-roaming conversations with other participants/experts. Participants normally gather around common topics of interest. Different activities/techniques can be used here based on brainstorming, synthesising information or just exchange o		
		Phase 3: Wrap-up	
Share-out	Participants representing the different conversations share highlights with the whole group.		

BACK NEXT

Choices you made

BIOVOICES Challenge Cluster

A - Market development

Group composition:

Civil society

Public administration

Group size

10-40

MML

Unconference

Tool steps

1. Select a suitable MML format

2. Select the right activities

3. Customize the agenda

4. Download supporting documents

As previously explained, the tool updates the right and left side lists. During this step, the tool attaches the chosen MML information and the step user is currently making, that is "Customize the agenda".

GOAL

Which is the goal you want to achieve?

- A - Networking
- B - Engagement
- C - Exploration
- D - Analysis
- E - Evaluation
- I don't know

BACK

This page represents the first step in choosing the right Activities. The tool asks users to choose a goal they want to achieve:

- A – Networking
- B – Engagement
- C – Exploration
- D – Analysis
- E - Evaluation

As per previous questions, users can choose “I don’t know” option. In addition to the “Choices you made” and “Tool steps” lists, the tool provides an Info panel in order to help users in making their choice with information regarding each goal.

Info

A - Networking: aims at fostering informal interaction and ice-breaking, setting the scene, building trust, creating a friendly, inclusive, safe atmosphere that facilitates discussion.

B - Engagement: fosters conversation and dialogue, enables people to express their thoughts, increases commitment and empowerment of the audience, and builds alignment.

C - Exploration: collects ideas on a topic, explores different options and scenarios, and facilitates sharing of different experiences and points of views.

D - Analysis: involves problem solving, item-mapping, explores cause-effects, interlinkages of items.

E - Evaluation: involves actions to provide and gather feedback on a specific topic, prioritize items, enables decision-making.

PARTICIPANT EXPERIENCE LEVEL

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface. At the top, there is a laptop icon with a checklist and a question mark. Below it, the question "Which is participant's experience level?" is displayed. Three options are listed: "Comparable" (highlighted in green), "Divergent", and "I don't know". A red rectangular box highlights the entire selection area. At the bottom, there is a green circular button labeled "BACK".

Users can choose the level of experience of the event participants.

- Comparable
- Divergent

The “I don’t know” choice is also present.

As per the previous page, in addition to the “Choices you made” and “Tool steps” lists, the tool provides an Info panel in order to help users in making their choice with information regarding each experience level.

The screenshot shows an "Info" panel with a green header. It contains two entries: "Comparable: members of the audience have similar level of expertise" and "Divergent: the audience is composed by people with different levels of expertise and backgrounds".

SESSION FORMAT

Which is the session format you want to use?

- Break-out
- Exhibition
- Plenary
- I don't know

BACK

The last question is about the session format users want to use.

- Break-out
- Exhibition
- Plenary

As mentioned before, the “I don’t know” choice is also present.

As per previous pages, the tool provides an Info panel in order to help users in making their choice with information regarding each session format.

Info

Plenary: One of the most common configuration styles of conferences. The audience is seating together in a room, facing to the speakers or presenters.

Break out session: The format denotes a event phase in which the participants break into smaller groups in order to focus on a specific sub-topic. The term includes a number of possible settings and suitable exercises/activities.

Exhibition: different stations are set around the room, usually displaying different types of information. People are able to freely roam from one to the next. Additionally, some kind of structured roaming can be provided, in the form of guided tours or lightning pitch programmes. It is useful to display large amounts of information in reduced space and short time.

AGENDA CUSTOMIZATION

Agenda customization

Agenda

Agenda item	Description	Timeline	Suitable activities
Phase 1: Setting the scene			
Kick-off	Participants arrive to the space, the facilitator(s) explains the rules of interaction, and the unconference agenda is collaboratively built	Insert time	Drag an activity
Phase 2: Working phase			
Conversations/discussion groups	Mostly based on free-roaming conversations with other participants/experts. Participants normally gather around common topics of interest. Different activities/techniques can be used here based on brainstorming, synthesising information or just exchange o		
Phase 3: Wrap-up			
Share-out	Participants representing the different conversations share highlights with the whole group		

I'M DONE WITH PHASE 1 CUSTOMIZATION

BACK

Activities

The best activities suggested are
Please drag the activity in the agenda

Setting the scene

- Lightning Talks [FACT SHEET](#)
- Speed Dating [FACT SHEET](#)
- Poster Session [FACT SHEET](#)

VIEW ALL SUGGESTIONS

Agenda customization consists of 3 steps:

- Setting the scene
- Working phase
- Wrap-up

Users can set up the activities for each phase. On the right side of the page, the tool provides the 3 best activities obtained through an analysis of the made choices.

Setting the scene

Lightning Talks	2.8	FACT SHEET
Speed Dating	2.6	FACT SHEET
Poster Session	2.4	FACT SHEET
Keynote Speakers	2.4	FACT SHEET
Digital Audience Response	2.2	FACT SHEET
Expert Panel	2.2	FACT SHEET
Role Play	2.0	FACT SHEET

Extra activities

Coffee break

Lunch break

HIDE ALL SUGGESTIONS BUTTON

Clicking on VIEW ALL SUGGESTIONS button, users can see all the available activities and their scores. To add one or more activities to the agenda, users can simply pick an activity up from the list on the right and drop it on the DRAG AN ACTIVITY space on the agenda. Users can also add the time chosen for the activity.

When all the activities of interest are successfully added, users can click on I'M DONE buttons to go to the next step.

REVIEW AND DOWNLOAD

Review and download

Summary

CHOSEN MML & ACTIVITIES

DOWNLOAD AGENDA

MML and knowledge exchange event FORMAT

Unconference

Lightning Talks

World Café

How-Now-Wow Matrix

High Five

FACTSHEET
DOWNLOAD FACTSHEET
DOWNLOAD METHODOLOGY

FACTSHEET
DOWNLOAD FACTSHEET

FACTSHEET
DOWNLOAD FACTSHEET

FACTSHEET
DOWNLOAD FACTSHEET

Once agenda customization is completed, the tool provides a tab that resumes all the choices made by the user. It contains the chosen MML and knowledge exchange event format and the list of activities. For each element, it is possible to view and download the related factsheet. Moreover, on the right side of the tab, there are two additional buttons:

DOWNLOAD METHODOLOGY:
To download a .PDF file with the methodology description and its phases.

Factsheet	
Name	Unconferences / Open Space conferences
Brief description	Unconferences involve a variety of gatherings, all of them based on high levels of participation and member-driven, where participants shape the agenda and are invited to participate one way or the other. Unconferences are "designed on the go", heavily based on attendee interests and particular needs. During the working group, attendees usually gather according to topics of interest, and are free to leave from one conversation to the next one. The focus is on topics of particular flexibility. Unconferences usually follow the principles of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Whatever comes and the right people. 2. Whatever happens is the anything that could have happened. 3. Whenever it starts is the right time and 4. When it's over, it's over
Methodology	<p>Before the event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define the general topic: compelling enough to attract interest and participation. Get the participants that could act as influencers and attract other attendees, and would be able to spark discussion easily. Find facilitators. Craft a compelling invitation. Choose a site for the event in an outdoor space, where participants could learn about the basics ("logistics, suggest topics and get familiar with the concept of "unconferences"). Set up registration. Recruit sponsors. Coordinate the event. Script the event: decide on facilitation techniques, select facilitators. <p>During the event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduce the event (location, topic, format) in a brief welcoming presentation. An on-facilitator could also be organized. Craft the agenda with the participants, define main topics of interests. Divide participants in groups if needed. Facilitate the conversation among participants. Collect results and solutions.
Estimated planning time needed	10-15h
Estimated budget needed	Low
Materials needed	Main entries: small rooms, paper material, whiteboard
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploration of topics Knowledge exchange Brainstorming ideas Networking

DOWNLOAD AGENDA:
To download a .DOC file with the agenda created through the process.

Agenda item	Description	Timeline	Suitable activities
Kick-off	Participants arrive to the location, the facilitator explains the topic of interaction, and the unconference agenda	Insert time	Lightning Talks
Conversations/discussion groups	Groups based on free-forming conversations with other participants/experts. Participants normally gather around common topics of interest. Different activities/experiences can be used here: based on brainstorming, synthesizing information or just exchange of	Insert time	World Café
Show-out	Participants representing the different conversations share highlights with the whole group	Insert time	How-Now-Wow Matrix
		Insert time	High Five

ICLEI provided the starting users' requirements

ICLEI and CNR provided the design of the MEED tool

LOBA provided images used for the layout

CNR implemented and manages the MEED tool

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BIOVOICES

CONNECTING BIO-BASED FORCES
FOR A SUSTAINABLE WORLD

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